

Sub-mm Displacement Measure via Multi-band Phase estimation in a Photonics-based Radar System

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Abstract— The phase coherence among multi-band signals generated by a photonics-based radar is exploited to perform differential phase estimation for enhanced displacement measures. The system employs stepped frequency continuous waves simultaneously in the S- and X-band, measuring the differential phase over a synthetic band up to 7.4GHz. The experimental results demonstrate a precision $< 200\mu\text{m}$ without using correction algorithms.

Keywords— *differential phase estimation, dual-band radar, microwave photonics, photonic transceiver.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural hazards produced by landslides and other ground failures are responsible for great damages, as human suffering, huge economic losses, and environmental degradation. Many strategies for reducing damages and impact from this kind of events have been proposed, for example, to develop a real-time monitoring and prediction capability in the regions most affected by landslides and applying remote sensing technologies [1]. Several different approaches for controlling and mapping the movement of ground displacements have been exploited as extensometers, crack meters, inclinometers, laser or sonar range finders, GPS receivers, etc. However, all these solutions provide only a localized deformation information and are, even for this reason, expensive and time consuming to be installed, as well as ineffective when monitoring broad areas, such as landslides monitoring on inaccessible areas [2]. To overcome these limitations, a remote sensing approach, based on radars, is well suited as it is able to provide complete and precise deformation maps of the whole area under surveillance [3]-[6].

Commercial radar relies on the Stepped-Frequency Continuous-Wave (SFCW) technique and differential interferometry [6]. The SFCW technique exploits several sinusoidal signals on a single RF band, all coherent to each other and with constant frequency separation, to illuminate the target. Target distance measurement is performed by evaluating the phase difference between the several frequency components of the SFCW signal [7]. The use of several sinusoidal waveforms allows to synthesize a large signal bandwidth for an improved range cell resolution and to reduce the system noise for an enhanced differential phase estimation. Also the quality

of the phase coherence among the sinusoidal waveforms has a big impact on the differential phase estimation. Once a precise measure of the phase of the echo signal is obtained, differential interferometry is used to evaluate the signal phase variations between two or more consecutive coherent observations of the same target. Such information can be translated into a very tiny range shift leading to very precise displacement measures.

Currently this technique is limited to the use of coherent sinusoidal waveforms in a single RF band, due to the issues in generating multi-band coherent signals. Moreover, the lack of highly stable tunable RF oscillators leads the commercial solutions to exploit only a fixed RF band.

However, the capability to exploit coherent multi-bands would be desirable to increase the synthesized signal bandwidth further improving the range cell resolution and the displacement measurement accuracy, as well as it would be desirable the possibility to tune the operative RF carriers for adapting the system to the environment and to the observation range [7]. This would impact on the final accuracy in reproducing the deformation maps contributing to a reliable early risk detection.

Over the past years, photonics technologies have been investigated as a means to overcome RF electronic device limitations. In [8] the authors realized the first demonstrator of a photonics-based coherent radar system that exploits photonics for the generation and detection of the RF signals without the use of noisy and narrow band mixers and replacing the RF clock with a highly stable optical clock. Using photonics, it has been also demonstrated the possibility of simultaneously generating and detecting several RF signals, in different RF bands guaranteeing an intrinsic high phase coherence among them, allowing coherent multiband radar operations [10].

Here we exploit the innovative features of the photonics-based radar for precise displacement measures. In fact, the huge bandwidth and flexibility of photonics allow to carry out an extended analysis based on SFCW and differential interferometry, exploiting different bands (two in this case) and with the capability to dynamically tune the RF operative carriers. The intrinsic high phase coherence between the used bands avoids the use of correction algorithms. Moreover the use of a single photonics-based transceiver able to handle all

Fig. 1. Left) Scheme of the developed radar experiment; Right) Electrical spectrum of the generated dual-band RF signal.

the RF carriers allows for a reduction of the whole system power consumption and footprint.

In particular, this paper reports for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, an experiment of small displacement measures based on SFCW technique and differential interferometry using a photonics-based coherent radar operating in S- and X-bands and synthesizing bandwidth up to 7.4 GHz, and it demonstrates the capability to reach an accuracy lower than $< 200\mu\text{m}$ over a range up to 3 km without correction algorithms.

II. OPERATION PRINCIPLE

The displacement monitoring is based on a differential phase measurements. In this technique the target is illuminated by several sinusoidal signals, coherent to each other, with frequency f_n and separation of Δf . Each frequency component of the backscattered echo accumulates a different phase shift φ_n , depending on the traveled distance d :

$$\varphi_n = 2\pi \cdot f_n \cdot \frac{2d}{c} \quad (1)$$

Thus, for a given range, two frequency separated by Δf will present a relative phase difference Φ

$$\Phi = 2\pi \cdot \Delta f \cdot \frac{2d}{c} \quad (2)$$

so that any change Δd in the distance induces a phase variation $\Delta\Phi$, and

$$\Delta d = \frac{c}{4\pi \cdot \Delta f} \cdot \Delta\Phi \quad (3)$$

If the phase varies more than 2π , ambiguities comes out. In fact this kind of technique presents an unambiguous range given by:

$$R_u = \frac{c}{2\Delta f} \quad (4)$$

Taking into account (3), it's worth to notice that a given precision in the phase estimation corresponds to a different accuracy in the range determination depending on Δf . Higher is the frequency difference, more precise is the distance measure, at the cost of reducing the unambiguous range.

To this aim, the photonic transceiver [10], guaranteeing the coherence between different frequency bands, provides an

extremely high Δf . Moreover its low phase noise allows a precise differential phase estimation, meaning a precise displacement measure.

III. PHOTONICS-BASED RADAR SYSTEM

The scheme of photonics-based dual-band radar systems exploited to perform the differential phase displacement measures is reported in Fig.1. The transceiver resorts to a mode-locked laser (MLL), which generates optical pulses with an extremely precise repetition rate of 400MHz, to upconvert and downconvert RF signals in different frequency bands. In details, at the transmitter side the laser is modulated in a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) by a direct digital synthesizer (DDS), generating the combination of two SFCW waveforms at the intermediate frequencies (IFs) of 75MHz and 125MHz. This way the waveforms are transferred as lower and upper sidebands around each optical mode of the MLL, and after the photodetection they result upconverted to every multiple frequency of the MLL. Finally, a set of electrical band-pass filters extract the replica of interest, at 2475MHz (S-band) and 9875MHz (X-band) as shown in Fig.1-Right, and a wideband amplifier (WBA) can boost the signal [10] to be transmitted by a Horn antenna. A second Horn antenna collects the echo, which is amplified by a WBA and used to modulate the laser pulses in another MZM. This performs the optical undersampling of the RF signal, so that after the photodetection the two waveforms are aliased back to their original IFs [10].

Finally, a 400MSample/s analog-to-digital converter (ADC) digitizes the signal, as well as a copy of the one generated by the DDS in order to obtain a phase reference.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

In order to demonstrate the effective operation of the system the two antennas (one for the transmission and one for the reception) are mounted on a digitally controlled motorized linear stage, capable of an accuracy of about $1\mu\text{m}$. In fact, due to practical limitations, the displacement measures are carried out by moving the antenna assembly and using the laboratory wall as fix target. The rail has been first positioned in the central position, taken as reference location, thus allowing to test both negative and positive target displacements.

The transmitted SFCW signal, whose spectrum is reported in Fig.1-Right, is composed by 20 frequency steps for each RF band, equally spaced by 1MHz, with a duration of 200 μ s each. This way it is possible to perform the standard radar processing [11] to obtain a rough range evaluation, with a precision given by the signal bandwidth of 20MHz, i.e. 7.5m. Moreover the differential phase technique provides 20 independent measures with a Δf of 7.4GHz, and since the unambiguous range in this case is only 2cm, other couples of tones with different Δf can eventually be used to resolve the ambiguities in this second stage of more precise range evaluation.

Fig. 2. FFT spectrum of the received downconverted signal.

The exploited signal processing consists on move the two acquired signals, i.e. the downconverted echo (Fig. 2) and the reference, to the frequency domain via a fast Fourier transform (FFT), multiply together the first one and the complex conjugate of the second, and evaluate the phase of each of the 40 tones.

Fig. 3-A shows the displacement measured by the radar system varying the position of the stage, by steps as small as 0.2mm and with a 10mm-long excursion.

Fig. 3. A) Measured displacement vs. real displacement; B) Difference between the real and the measured displacements.

The results demonstrate a good agreement between real position and displacement evaluated by the system. The error between the measured and the real displacement in each point, reported in Fig. 3-B, is limited to less than ± 0.2 mm.

In a real application, such as mine or structural monitoring, the target could be located up to few km distant, thus the

Fig. 4. Cross-correlation function of the received echo for 0km (blue), 1.5km (red) and 3 km (green) distant targets.

Fig. 5. Mean error of the displacement measurement error.

measure has been repeated for different target distances. Since a source of error in the phase difference estimation is also the intrinsic phase noise of the radar system, adding a delay between the signal generation and reception decorrelates the echo and the reference signal, thus providing a better estimations of the performance.

The distance has been simulated by adding one and two 1km-long optical fiber spools in the transceiver as delays that, since the refractive index of fibers is about 1.5, emulate a distance of 1.5km and 3km.

The range cell, i.e. the target distance, has been measured by evaluating the peak of cross-correlation function between the collected echo and the reference signal. As shown in Fig. 4, in which the blue plot reports the 0km case, the red plot the 1.5km target and the green one the 3km target, the measured ranges perfectly match with the nominal length of the fiber spools.

Regarding the accuracy of the differential phase estimation, the mean absolute error for displacement measure at different ranges is reported in Fig. 5. As can be seen the error remains almost constant and below 0.2mm, thus confirming that the phase stability of the developed radar system is suitable for phase interferometry techniques.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we proposed for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, a displacement measure experiment based on multiband SFCW with differential interferometry, that has been enabled by the use of a photonics-based radar. In fact the use of

photonics allows for the generation and detection of tunable and multi-band RF signals with intrinsic high phase coherence that allows to obtain sub-mm resolution without correction errors.

In the proposed experiment the photonics-based radar transceiver exploits a mode locked laser to generate 40 coherent sinusoidal waveforms distributed in S- and X- bands, synthesizing a band of 7.4 GHz.

Experimental results demonstrate an accuracy $< 200\mu\text{m}$ for displacement measurements up to 3km of distance.

The use of a single photonics-based transceiver for handling the signals in both the RF bands allows for a reduction of the power consumption and footprint of the whole system.

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